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Alternative Railway Line/Points Heating using Thermoelectric Heating

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Abstract: Railway points and track without any form of heating can fail under challenging cold weather conditions due to freezing, leading to service disruption, train delays, cancellation and speed restrictions that impact on customer satisfaction with the railway network and train operator. This paper investigates the novel use of thermoelectric heating as an alternative to the most commonly implemented solution of electric strip resistive points heaters used by Network Rail in the UK. The design and practical implementation of a small-scale laboratory experiment set-up, test procedure, and test results are presented that demonstrate the heating and performance characteristics of a Network Rail approved electric strip heater, and a novel thermoelectric heating solution, to determine if thermoelectric heating is suitable for this industrial application. The results demonstrate the thermoelectric system successfully raises the temperature of a railway line test piece from ambient room temperature conditions, similar to an electric strip heater, with further work required to optimise the design and obtain practical test results at lower ambient temperatures where freezing prevention will be required. The application of thermoelectricity to heating and de-icing railway points and track is a new and novel area, and represents an opportunity to develop a different technological approach and solution.

Keywords: railway points heating, railway points de-icing, thermoelectricity, thermoelectric heating, electric strip heaters

Main highlights:

A novel thermoelectric heating system, and a standard Network Rail approved electric strip heater typically used for railway line points heating and freezing prevention, have been evaluated in a small-scale practical test set-up and both systems demonstrate a 1.2 metre railway line test piece can be heated above ambient room temperature. This is a new and novel application for thermoelectric heating systems and will be developed further to identify the relative advantages and disadvantages of the system when compared with the standard industry solution, and if the thermoelectric system is a viable alternative.

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Introduction

The UK railway network is one of the largest transport networks in the country, and maintaining the operations capability of the railway points and track can be difficult without any form of heating under challenging winter weather conditions due to freezing, leading to service disruption, speed restrictions, train delays, cancellations, and customer dissatisfaction. Modern points heaters use electric heating elements clipped to the rails to heat a set of points to prevent ice forming, and to keep the switch blades moving, but this solution can be inefficient, often taking up to two hours to reach operating temperature, and may still lead to points failure. This paper aims to investigate thermoelectric heating as an alternative technology to achieve railway points heating. The paper gives a brief overview of the railway line/points heating systems most often used in the UK, and the background theory necessary to understand the principle of thermoelectric heating. A small-scale practical test system is presented that is suitable to demonstrate the heating and performance characteristics of the current electric strip heater, and a novel thermoelectric heating solution, with several test results presented and discussed. The paper draws conclusions on the test results presented, and highlights opportunities for future work to demonstrate the relative advantages and disadvantages of using thermoelectric heating.

Current UK Railway Points Heating Systems

Railway points heating helps to maintain the normal operation of the railway network in adverse winter weather conditions by preventing the switch rails from freezing at the point end, maintaining their switch movement and operation, and from snow accumulating between the switch and stock rails. Since around 1970, electricity has been used for points heating within the UK railway network, and the most common method used by Network Rail is electric strip heaters, clipped to the rails to heat a set of points, that operate on the principle of electric current passing through a resistive conducting material which generates heat. This generated heat is sufficient to de-ice and maintain the points switch operation in adverse weather conditions. The electric strip heater is typically powered by a trackside transformer that steps-down the supply voltage from 230V to 110V single phase AC at 50Hz, or a transformer with secondary side full wave bridge rectifiers supplying 110V DC may be used if necessary for signalling system immunity. The transformer is used to isolate the stock and switch rails on each side of the track, via separate windings. to ensure heater failure cannot cause maloperation of signalling systems. A temperature controller is located in a nearby control cubicle, which also incorporates circuit protection and auxiliary circuits, and the cubicle powers multiple points heating transformers. The controller energises the transformer primaries via a dedicated switching contactor, and is of the on/off type, reading the rail temperature via dedicated external rail mounted thermistor type sensor probes installed on the closest point to the control cubicle. The sensor probes are used to detect the temperature of the 'hot' rail to be heated, and a 'cold' rail of a typical point supplied by the control cubicle. The control cubicle is also provided with an externally mounted precipitation sensor. The sensors provide the temperature controller with the information required to automatically turn-on and turn-off the electric strip heater, and the precipitation sensor adjusts the controller set-point thresholds if rain or snowfall is detected, reducing the risk of the railway points freezing in severe weather conditions [1].

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Throughout the UK's heavy rail network, outside of London, trackside rail infrastructure is mainly under Network Rail ownership and use San Electro Heat or Tuerk-Hillinger electric strip heating elements, either being on, and at full power, or turned off. Positive Temperature Coefficient (PTC) 'self-regulating' type tape, which is not used extensively by Network Rail, but is used by Irish Rail, London Underground Ltd, private depots and various UK light rail operators, has also gained approval for use within different networks. There is evidence of the use of induction heating in international railway networks, particularly in Sweden by Indheater, and have been evaluated for use in other countries [2-3], although the use and application in the UK railway network is limited and relatively new. The application of thermoelectricity for heating railway points is a new and novel area, and represents an opportunity to develop a different technological approach and solution.

Thermoelectric heating

If DC current is applied to the input terminals of a thermoelectric module, sometimes referred to as a Peltier module, the module will operate as a thermoelectric heater and provide localised heating of an object connected to one side of the module as a heat pump. If the polarity of the DC current applied to the module input terminals is reversed, the module will operate as a thermoelectric cooler and provide localised cooling of the object connected to it, with the other side of the module increasing in temperature [4].

In Fig. 1, an object to be heated is attached to the 'cold' side of the thermoelectric module, referred to as T_C . When DC current is applied to the module's input terminals, due to the Peltier effect, heat from the surrounding atmosphere will be absorbed by the hot side of the thermoelectric module, referred to as T_H , which is normally attached to a heat sink, and transferred or 'pumped' through to the cold side of the module along with additional joule heating developed within the device due to the supply current.

If the polarity of the DC current applied to the thermoelectric module input terminals is reversed, as shown in Fig. 2, electrical current flows from the positive terminal of the supply to the negative terminal and is shown as a clockwise current flow, and the module will cool the object connected to the 'cold' side of the module due to the Peltier effect. Hence, it is possible to use the same thermoelectric module for heating and cooling dependent on the polarity of the DC input voltage, and therefore the direction of input current flow [5-6].

It should be noted the definition for which side of the module is referred to as the 'cold' or 'hot' side is arbitrary and may differ between publications and authors. In this paper, the cold side of the module has been referenced to the side of the module most often used in thermoelectric publications for consistency, with the bulk of publications focusing on thermoelectric cooling rather than heating.

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Fig. 1. A thermoelectric module operating as a thermoelectric heater [6]

Fig. 2. A thermoelectric module operating as a thermoelectric cooler [6]

Test system and test method

A test system was designed and built to demonstrate the operating characteristics of both the standard heating solution using electric strip heating, providing a performance target and benchmark, and a novel thermoelectric heating system in a similar test setup.

Standard heating system – electric strip heating

To determine the operating characteristics of the standard heating solution in free air, a San Electro Heat BR1002, 200 watt, electric strip heater was connected to a single phase AC supply of 110V at 50Hz and allowed to reach operating temperature under ambient conditions. The temperature of the heater element was measured by several K-type thermocouples, attached in the positions shown in Fig. 3, connected to a Pico Technology TC08 thermocouple datalogger and standard windows laptop PC for data collection and analysis.

The test system was modified to include a 1.2 metre length of standard UK railway line made from rolled steel, part number NR 60, mounted onto two wood battens to create a stable test platform. The San Electro Heat strip heater was connected to a 110V, 50 Hz, single phase AC supply and attached to the railway line as shown in Fig. 4. The temperature of the railway line was measured by several K-type thermocouples, located in the positions shown, and the thermal profile of the railway line test piece was obtained when the electric strip heater was turned on and allowed to reach operating temperature.

Fig. 3. Electric strip heater temperature measurement

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Fig. 4. Electric strip heater mounted onto 1.2 metre railway line test piece

A Network Rail approved Findlay Irvine ICELERT 407M controller was added to the test system, as shown in Fig. 5, and set to control the temperature of the heater strip at 7°C above ambient. The temperature controller uses a ‘hot rail’ temperature sensor to determine the temperature of the railway line test piece, and compares this with a ‘cold rail’ temperature sensor which was set to read ambient temperature. The thermal profile of the railway line test piece was obtained when the electric strip heater was controlled by the temperature controller.

Fig. 5 Temperature controller connected to electric strip heater mounted onto 1.2 metre railway line test piece

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Thermoelectric heating system

A single Tark Thermal Solutions CP14-127-045L thermoelectric module, measuring 40 mm in length, 40 mm in width, and 3.3 mm in depth, was mounted onto a Thermo Electric Devices TDEX6015/TH heat sink measuring 60 mm in length x 60 mm in width x 16 mm in depth, and attached to the 1.2 metre railway line test piece, as shown in Fig. 6. A G-clamp was used to secure the thermoelectric module and heat sink assembly to the railway line for test purposes, and thermal paste was applied to both sides of the module to ensure good thermal contact was made between the module and the railway line, and the module and attached heat sink. The thermoelectric module input terminals were connected for thermoelectric heating to a DC supply of 15V at 5.5A. This DC supply voltage and current was chosen to achieve a high rate of heating, remaining within the module maximum specification limit of 15.4V and 8.5A. It was also important to ensure the temperature difference between both sides of the thermoelectric module, when operating as a thermoelectric heater, did not exceed the maximum module specification limit of 75°C and an operating temperature of 80°C [7]. As the thermoelectric module is in direct contact with the railway line test piece, the temperature and thermal mass of the railway line enables a thermoelectric module input voltage and current close to the maximum module specification to be used. The temperature of the railway line was measured by several K-type thermocouples, attached in the positions shown, connected to a Pico Technology TC08 thermocouple datalogger and PC. The thermal profile of the railway line test piece was obtained when the thermoelectric heater was turned on and allowed to reach operating temperature.

Fig. 6 Single thermoelectric module and heat sink mounted onto 1.2 metre railway line

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The single thermoelectric module and heat sink assembly was replaced by two separate thermoelectric modules and heat sinks of the same type, connected to a DC source of 15V at 5.5A, and mounted onto the railway line test piece as shown in Fig. 7. The temperature of the railway line was measured by several K-type thermocouples attached in the positions shown, and the thermal profile of the railway line test piece was obtained when the two thermoelectric modules were turned on and allowed to reach operating temperature.

Fig. 7 Two thermoelectric modules and heat sink assemblies mounted onto 1.2 metre railway line test piece

Results

The practical test results obtained for the standard heating solution using electric strip heating is presented first, followed by the test results for the thermoelectric heating system in a similar test setup.

Standard heating system – electric strip heating

The San Electro Heat 200 watt electric strip heater element connected as shown in Fig. 3, when turned-on and allowed to reach operating temperature, demonstrated an average temperature of 331°C across the five thermocouple measurement points, with the highest temperature of 361°C observed at thermocouple 4 and the lowest temperature of 241°C at thermocouple 1, shown in Fig. 8. The range between thermocouples 2 to 5 was 16°C and it is observed that thermocouple 1 is significantly lower in temperature. Thermocouple 1 is located 5 cm from the end of the heater strip and the reduced temperature may be due to how the heater strip is terminated. The ambient temperature was 21°C throughout the experiment.

The San Electro Heat electric strip heater was then mounted onto the railway line test piece and supplied with 110V single phase AC as shown in Fig. 4. The results, shown in Fig. 9, demonstrate the electric strip heater reaches a maximum temperature of 124°C measured by thermocouple 6, raising the temperature of the railway line from an ambient of 21°C to an average across the other thermocouples 1 to 7, excluding thermocouple 6, of 43°C with a range of 16°C.

Fig. 8 Electric strip heater element operating temperature in free air when supplied with 110V single phase AC

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Fig. 9 Electric strip heater attached to 1.2 metre railway line test piece

A Findlay Irvine ICEALERT 407M temperature controller was added to the test system, as shown in Fig. 5, and set to control the temperature of the electric strip heater to 7°C above ambient. The results, shown in Fig. 10, demonstrate the controller and electric strip heater maintain the average temperature of the railway line across thermocouples 1 to 7 at 29°C, which is 7°C above the ambient temperature of 22°C. Thermocouple 7 records the highest temperature of 34°C, with thermocouple 1 the lowest at 27°C. The operating temperature of the electric strip heater, shown by thermocouple 6, cycles between a peak of 151°C, and a low of 29°C, as the heater is turned-on and turned-off by the temperature controller.

Fig. 10 Temperature controller and electric strip heater attached to 1.2 metre railway line

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Thermoelectric heating system

When the single thermoelectric module and heat sink assembly was mounted onto the railway line test piece shown in Fig. 6, and supplied by a DC source of 15V at 5.5A, the results in Fig. 14 demonstrate the module successfully heats the railway line to an average temperature of 31°C across thermocouples 1 to 7. The highest temperature of 59°C was observed at thermocouple 6, and the lowest of 25°C at thermocouples 1 and 3. The ambient temperature throughout the test was 20°C.

With two thermoelectric modules and heat sink assemblies mounted onto the railway line test piece shown in Fig. 7, and supplied by a DC source of 15V at 5.5A, the results in Fig. 15 demonstrate improved performance, with the modules successfully heating the railway line faster and to a higher temperature. The average temperature across thermocouples 1 to 7 was 45°C, with the highest temperature of 65°C observed at thermocouple 7, and the lowest of 37°C at thermocouples 1 and 3. The ambient temperature throughout the test was 22°C.

Fig. 14. Single thermoelectric module and heat sink attached to 1.2 metre railway line

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Fig. 15. Two thermoelectric modules and heat sinks attached to 1.2 metre railway line

Discussion

The aim and motivation of this work was to establish if thermoelectric heating could be applied as an alternative to the electric strip heaters currently used for the prevention of freezing in railway line points. A small-scale practical test set-up was designed and built to demonstrate and benchmark the heating and performance characteristics of a common electric strip heater used by Network Rail in the UK, and compare the results with a novel thermoelectric heating solution. The practical test results demonstrate the electric strip heater, in free-air, heats from ambient to an average temperature of 331°C, and when attached to a 1.2 metre length of railway line, heats the railway line from an ambient of 21°C to an average of 43°C. When a Network Rail approved temperature controller is added to the system and set to control at 7°C above ambient, the railway line test piece average temperature is maintained at 29°C, which is 7°C above the ambient temperature of 22°C observed during the test. In comparison, the results for thermoelectric heating are encouraging, demonstrating a single thermoelectric module successfully heats the railway line test piece from an ambient temperature of 20°C to an average temperature of 31°C. Improved performance can be observed by using two thermoelectric modules, with faster heating of the railway line test piece from an ambient temperature of 22°C to an average of 45°C. The results demonstrate a thermoelectric solution, with optimised design, can heat a railway line test piece above ambient room temperature, and should be the focus of further investigation and work. Further work is required to demonstrate the operation of the thermoelectric modules with a temperature controller, to compare directly with a Network Rail approved electric strip heater and temperature controller, and to test the systems at lower ambient temperatures where prevention of freezing will be required.

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Conclusions

The design and implementation of a small-scale test system to demonstrate the heating and performance characteristics of an electric strip heater, and a novel thermoelectric heating system, for railway points and freezing prevention has been presented. The test results obtained for the current Network Rail solution of an electric strip heater and temperature controller can be used as a benchmark and target to optimise the design of a novel thermoelectric heating solution. Initial practical test results for the thermoelectric system are encouraging, and demonstrate the system can heat a railway line test piece above ambient room temperature in a reasonable time period. Further work is required to optimise the thermoelectric heating system design, demonstrate operation with a temperature controller, and obtain practical test results for both systems at lower ambient temperatures where freezing prevention will be required. The relative advantages, disadvantages, and feasibility of the thermoelectric solution can then be established and compared with a current Network Rail approved electric strip heater system.

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